

FACTORS AFFECTING TEACHING-LEARNING EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS OF METRO DUMAGUETE COLLEGE

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ABSTRACT

This study delves into the factors affecting teaching-learning effectiveness of teachers and students. The study was conducted at Metro Dumaguete College, comprised of 346 respondents, both male and female. The primary instrument used to gather important data was a validated self-made survey questionnaire. Through this, the factors affecting teaching-learning effectiveness of teachers and students were assessed. The researcher employed statistical tool such as Weighted Mean. These provided clarification and rationale for the study's findings. The analysis revealed that students generally perceive their teachers to be highly effective, particularly in communication and fostering student engagement, with the highest mean scores. Learning effectiveness was also rated positively, with the helpfulness of learning materials receiving a very high mean score. Factors influencing teaching-learning effectiveness, such as teachers' pedagogical skills, were deemed highly impactful, evidenced by a very high mean score. Additionally, the study highlighted the importance of diverse teaching strategies and emphasized the need for instructional differentiation and flexibility. There was an indication of potential for improvement in technology integration, particularly through game-based instruction, which could enhance student engagement and motivation. Practical assessments and positive teacher-student relationships were also highlighted as significant factors. These insights underscore the multifaceted nature of effective teaching and the importance of creating a supportive, engaging, and technology-enhanced learning environment at Metro Dumaguete College. The findings provide valuable guidance for refining

teaching practices to better meet diverse student needs and enhance overall learning outcomes.

Keywords: *teaching-learning effectiveness, pedagogical skills, student engagement, instructional strategies, technology integration, game-based instruction, practical assessments, teacher-student relationships, learning materials, educational environment, differentiated instruction*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching effectiveness and learning effectiveness play pivotal roles in shaping students' academic journeys within the educational landscape. Recognizing and comprehending the various factors that influence these elements are imperative for educators and administrators dedicated to improving the overall educational experience. This exploration intricately examines the multifaceted factors impacting teaching and learning, with the goal of unraveling the intricate dynamics that either contribute to or impede the effectiveness of these fundamental processes.

It is crucial to conduct a detailed analysis of the various aspects influencing the efficacy of teaching and learning in the dynamic field of education, where changes happen quickly. Determining these variables not only facilitates the development of focused tactics to improve academic results but also supports the main goal of fostering a nurturing and stimulating learning environment. Understanding the complex interactions between teachers, students, curricula, and institutional contexts is made easier with the help of this investigation. As a result, it creates the framework for interventions and forward-thinking developments in teaching methods, guaranteeing a flexible and adaptable response to the changing demands of students and the educational environment.

Teacher effectiveness concerns the efficacy of specific types of instruction on students' learning. Numerous local and international research studies have investigated the challenges encountered in the teaching and learning processes. These challenges encompass classroom management, environmental factors, instructional methods, and supervisory challenges. Boakye and Ampiah (2017), discovered that teachers had to deal with a number of issues related to teaching, including a lack of content knowledge, time management issues, insufficient teaching resources for effective learning, and students' disinterest in the learning process, which made it difficult for them to understand the lessons that were taught. Additionally, Bukoye (2019), pointed out that low usage of teaching and learning resources in lessons leads to ineffective management of classrooms and delivery of content.

Consequently, conducting a study on factors affecting teaching-learning effectiveness is instrumental in ensuring that MDC remains responsive, adaptable, and committed to providing high-quality education that meets the evolving needs of both learners and the educational landscape.

Research Questions

The study aims to investigate the factors affecting teaching-learning effectiveness of teachers and students of Metro Dumaguete College. Specifically, the study seeks to address the following questions:

1. What is the extent of factors affecting the teaching-learning effectiveness of teachers as perceived by students in terms of:
 - 1.1. Teaching effectiveness and
 - 1.2. Learning effectiveness?

2. What is the extent to which the following factors impact teaching-learning effectiveness:
 - 2.1. Class size;
 - 2.2. Teacher-student relationships;
 - 2.3. Classroom environment;
 - 2.4. Use of technology;
 - 2.5. Program design;
 - 2.6. Assessment and evaluation methods;
 - 2.7. Teachers' pedagogical skills;
 - 2.8. Student motivation; and
 - 2.9. Resources and facilities?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive quantitative approach as a research design to assess the extent to which some identified factors affects teaching-learning effectiveness of teachers and students of Metro Dumaguete College. According to Creswell (2009), a quantitative method is the most suitable research design when the study's objective is to examine the extent of effectiveness. Therefore, employing this research design was expected to answer questions related to teaching-learning effectiveness. Stratified sampling technique was employed in identifying the respondents. The Slovin formula was used to identify the sample size per college/department or program. Students were selected based on their courses. The sample respondents included those enrolled in the following programs: BS in Computer Science (19), BS in Information Technology (19), BS in Tourism Management (30), BSBA majoring in Financial Management and Marketing Management (24), BTVTEd majoring in Computer Hardware Servicing (5), Diploma in Digital Arts (61), Diploma in Software Engineering Technology (65), Diploma in Tourism Technology (93), Diploma in Vocational Teacher Education Technology (7), and Senior High School students from the following strands: ABM (4), TVL-HE and ICT (6), GAS (3), and HUMSS (10). The sample population comprised of 346 students. Questionnaires were distributed through surveys and given to students from different year levels based on the assigned sample size per course.

The data were then analyzed using the weighted mean to identify the factors affecting teaching-learning effectiveness of teachers and students. The questionnaires were divided into three different sections such as perceived teaching effectiveness,

perceived learning effectiveness, and factors that impact teaching-learning effectiveness, and all the items used 5-point Likert scales.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 presents students' perceptions of their teachers' teaching effectiveness across various dimensions, represented by the mean scores ($w\bar{x}$) and the extent of teaching effectiveness (ETE). Overall, the majority of students perceived their teachers to be highly effective in various aspects of teaching. Specifically, two indicators, namely 'teacher communicates the subject matter clearly and effectively' and 'encourages active student participation and engagement in the learning process,' obtained the highest weighted means ($w\bar{x}$) of 4.31 and 4.28, respectively. This indicates a very high extent of teaching effectiveness as perceived by the students.

Table 1.1
Students' Perceptions on the Teachers Teaching Effectiveness (n= 346)

Perceptions of Teaching Effectiveness		$w\bar{x}$	ETE
1.	The teacher communicates the subject matter clearly and effectively.	4.31	VH
2.	The teacher encourages active student participation and engagement in the learning process.	4.28	VH
3.	The teacher provides timely and constructive feedback on assignments and assessments.	4.08	H
4.	The teacher uses a variety of teaching methods and resources to cater to different learning styles.	3.12	M
5.	The teacher demonstrates enthusiasm and passion for the subject matter.	3.54	H
6.	The teacher creates a positive and inclusive classroom environment that promotes learning.	3.92	H
7.	The teacher effectively manages classroom disruptions and maintains discipline.	3.70	H
8.	The teacher sets clear learning objectives and goals for the course.	4.05	H
Composite		3.87	H
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Equivalent (VE)	Extent of Teaching Effectiveness (ETE)
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Moderately Agree (MA)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Agree (A)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Minimal (M)
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Not at All (NA)

Table 1.2 displays students' perceptions of their learning effectiveness, measured by various indicators such as the helpfulness of learning materials, understanding of subject matter, motivation and engagement, feedback provision, alignment of activities with objectives, comfort in seeking clarification, consideration of learning needs, and confidence in applying knowledge.

Table 1.2
Students' Perceptions on their Learning Effectiveness (n= 346)

Perceptions of Learning Effectiveness		$w\bar{x}$	ETE
1.	The learning Materials provided by the teacher are helpful and relevant to the students' needs.	4.23	VH
2.	The students are able to grasp and understand the subject matter due to the teaching methods used.	3.26	M
3.	The students are motivated and engaged in the learning process.	3.41	H

4. The students are provided constructive feedback that helps them improve in their understanding of the subject.	3.73	H
5. The learning activities and assignments are aligned with the learning objectives.	3.92	H
6. The students are comfortable asking questions and seeking clarification from the teacher.	3.76	H
7. The students' learning needs and preferences are taken into account by the teacher.	3.84	H
8. The students show confidence in applying the knowledge gained in real-life situations.	3.82	H
Composite	3.75	H

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Equivalent (VE)	Extent of Teaching Effectiveness (ETE)
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Moderately Agree (MA)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Agree (A)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Minimal (M)
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Not at All (NA)

Table 2 presents students' perceptions of various factors that impact teaching-learning effectiveness, including class size, teacher-student relationship, classroom environment, use of technology, curriculum/program design, assessment and evaluation methods, teachers' pedagogical skills, student motivation, parental involvement, and resources and facilities.

Table 2
Extent to which the following Factors Impact on the Teaching-Learning Effectiveness (n=346)

Perceptions of Learning Effectiveness	$w\bar{x}$	LE
Class Size	4.03	HE
Teacher-Student Relationship	4.10	HE
Classroom Environment	3.97	HE
Use of Technology	4.02	HE
Curriculum/ Program Design	3.98	HE
Assessment and Evaluation Methods used	4.10	HE
Teachers' Pedagogical Skills used/ shown in a class	4.25	VHE
Student Motivation	4.04	HE
Parental Involvement	3.88	HE
Resources and Facilities	4.05	HE
Composite	4.04	HE

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Equivalent (VE)
	4.21 – 5.00	Very High Extent (VHE)
	3.41 – 4.20	High Extent (HE)
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately High (MH)
	1.81 – 2.60	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Very Low (VL)

Table 3.a below presents a comprehensive list of specific methods that students believe are most important in facilitating learning. These methods encompass various teaching strategies, instructional approaches, and learning activities aimed at enhancing student engagement, interaction, and understanding in diverse classroom settings. Students emphasize the importance of using the most effective teaching methods that cater to diverse learning needs and preferences, suggesting the need for instructional differentiation and flexibility.

Table 3.a

Other Comments and Suggestions of the Students

A. The Specific Methods Students believed are most important in Facilitating Learning
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Teachers must use the most effective teaching methods that will enhance students learning in a diverse classroom. • Face to face classes must be imposed in all subjects. • Encouragement by the teacher is the most important in facilitating learning. • Methods that require student-teacher interaction. • The most effective strategy is the collaborative one; students can learn better when exposed to group settings. • Hands on activity and collaborative strategies • Differentiated instruction • The use of instructional materials that is more captivating • Modeling • Allowing the students to experience what they have learned in theory • Varied assessment and meaningful use of visual aids • Inclusive strategy since there are students in a class who are mentally challenged • Individualized instruction • Interactive approach • Technology Integration • Problem-solving method • Student -centered strategies • Game-based is most effective for us 21st century learners • Expository methods • Inquiry-based approach • Project-based learning

Table 3.b below suggests that there is room for improvement in integrating technology into the teaching-learning process, as indicated by several key points raised by respondents. Respondents emphasize the importance of integrating game-based instruction into the classroom, highlighting its potential to enhance student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. This approach leverages gamification principles to make learning more interactive, immersive, and enjoyable for students.

Table 3.b

Technology can be Better Integrated into the Teaching-learning Process

<i>B. Technology can be better integrated into the teaching-learning process</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology can be better integrated in the class if the game- based instruction is practiced in the classroom and the teacher must have enough technology in the classroom. By simply showing their laptop the students in the whole class cannot fully visualize the lesson because the screen is limited to the nearest students only. • By integrating game-based. • More meaningful ppts and Multi-media presentations that incudes illustrations, appropriate pictures. • Multimedia should be effectively integrated • Using the online assessment tools • Provide activities that is technology-based and game-based

Table 3.c reveal several factors that respondents believe play a significant role in teaching-learning effectiveness. Respondents emphasize the importance of hands-on, practical assessments over traditional written forms. This approach allows students to demonstrate their understanding and application of knowledge through tangible, real-world tasks and activities.

Table 3.c

Factors not mentioned in the questionnaire Students think play a significant role in teaching-learning effectiveness

<i>C. Factors not mentioned in the questionnaire Students think play a significant role in teaching-learning effectiveness</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final assessment of Learning should be hands on not in written form. • Teachers should handle the classes not just in group discussions and just letting students to watch YouTube videos. • Teachers must be equipped with technological skills so that they can effectively teach the lesson. • More student and teacher interactions are more effective. The teachers should facilitate the teaching and learning process. • Improve the teaching skills of the teachers. • More on student and teachers' interactions. Let the students speak. • Teachers' promptness in coming to the class is one factor that can affects students' interest in coming to school. • Building positive relationship with students. • Teachers must establish good rapport with the students. • Game-based and teachers must be technologically equipped first to effectively integrate game base. • Teachers must be equipped with technology and internet connectivity is important in utilizing the technology-based approach. • Teachers must provide visuals. • Face to face classes in all subjects is the most effective teaching modality. • Multimedia should be creative and eye catching

Table 3.d shows the feedback provided by respondents that provides valuable insights into their perspectives on effective teaching practices and classroom dynamics. Their comments underscore the multifaceted nature of effective teaching, emphasizing the significance of fostering a supportive, engaging, and technology-enhanced learning environment that accommodates diverse student needs while promoting active learning and critical thinking.

Table 3.d
Other Comments and Suggestions

D. OTHER COMMENTS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers must provide varied examples so that we can fully understand the lesson. • It is good if the teachers will also provide the learning materials like ppts/ modules • Better if the teacher will provide activities that will cater the different level of thinking of students in a class • Equipped the teachers with technology like functional tvs in all classes so that it is also easier for the students to understand what they have discussed • Develop the 21st century skills of the learners • Provide supportive learning environment • Better if the teachers will use visuals during discussion. • Learning will take place if we are comfortable inside the class • Good classroom management will also promote better learning • Teachers must manage the behavior of the students so that learning will take place • Teachers who challenge the students on how to reason out is important in shaping their minds. • A teacher must be a good communicator • Make the class more enjoyable by applying varied teaching strategies • Good coaching to students will help us learn and interested in the class • Provide activities that required critical analysis • Different strategies to make the class more engaging • Face to face classes is most effective than online • It would be better if the teachers will give a short quiz or checkup activity after each discussion to preserve learning • Teachers must know how to process the discussion • Teachers must know how to simplify the discussion • teacher must know how to explain. do not depend on the reporters. • <i>They should have passion to teach so that they won't always absent in the class.</i> • <i>"I should suggest that who really hires the teachers, you should see to it that they love their job because some of the teachers here in MDC are quite "tapulan", they don't discuss properly and always absent. last semester we had a teacher -male "wala jud klase2.</i>

DISCUSSION

Students' Perceptions on the Teachers Teaching Effectiveness

Table 1.1 presents students' perceptions of their teachers' teaching effectiveness across various dimensions, represented by the mean scores ($w\bar{x}$) and the extent of teaching effectiveness (ETE). Overall, the majority of students perceived their teachers to be highly effective in various aspects of teaching. Specifically, two indicators, namely 'teacher communicates the subject matter clearly and effectively' and 'encourages active student participation and engagement in the learning process,' obtained the highest weighted means ($w\bar{x}$) of 4.31 and 4.28, respectively. This indicates a very high extent of teaching effectiveness as perceived by the students.

The data implies that the high score for clear and effective communication indicates that teachers are successfully conveying subject matter, essential for student comprehension and learning. Additionally, the strong perception of encouraging active student participation suggests that teachers are effectively engaging students in the learning process, fostering a dynamic classroom environment. While the moderate score for 'using a variety of teaching methods indicates a potential area for enhancement, incorporating diverse teaching approaches can cater to different learning styles and enhance overall learning outcomes. Furthermore, the positive perception of teachers demonstrating enthusiasm and passion for the subject matter is crucial for inspiring students and enhancing their interest in learning.

Communication clarity and effectiveness have long been recognized as crucial components of effective teaching (Allen, et al., 2020). When teachers articulate concepts clearly and coherently, students are better able to comprehend and engage with the material, leading to enhanced learning outcomes (Dyck & Allen, 2019). Moreover, effective communication fosters a conducive learning environment wherein students feel encouraged to participate actively in class discussions and activities (Zhao, et al., 2021). The emphasis on active student participation aligns with contemporary pedagogical approaches that prioritize student-centered learning and engagement (Freeman, et al., 2019).

The high ratings for these indicators may also reflect the increasing emphasis on interactive teaching methodologies and the integration of technology in the classroom (Hodges, et al., 2019). Teachers who utilize multimedia resources, interactive presentations, and collaborative activities are perceived by students as more engaging and effective instructors (Kay & LeSage, 2019). Additionally, the shift towards personalized and adaptive learning experiences has allowed teachers to cater to diverse learning styles and preferences, further enhancing teaching effectiveness (Van Leeuwen, et al., 2020).

In conclusion, the findings underscore the importance of clear communication and active student engagement in fostering teaching effectiveness. By attending to these aspects, educators can create dynamic learning environments that promote student learning and achievement. However, it is essential to acknowledge that perceptions of teaching effectiveness may vary among students and across different contexts, necessitating ongoing assessment and reflection by educators (Trigwell & Prosser, 2019).

Students' Perceptions on their Learning Effectiveness

Table 1.2 displays students' perceptions of their learning effectiveness, measured by various indicators such as the helpfulness of learning materials, understanding of subject matter, motivation and engagement, feedback provision, alignment of activities with objectives, comfort in seeking clarification, consideration of learning needs, and confidence in applying knowledge. Overall, students perceive their learning experience positively across most dimensions/indicators. It can be noticed that helpful and relevant learning materials provided by their teachers received a very high score or weighted mean ($w\bar{x}$) of 4.23, indicating a very high extent of effectiveness.

This suggests that teachers are providing learning materials that meet students' needs, essential for facilitating effective learning experiences and enhancing understanding. However, the score or weighted mean ($w\bar{x}$) for students' ability to grasp subject matter is only moderate (3.26), indicating opportunities to improve teaching methods to ensure better understanding and comprehension among students.

This result can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, it underscores the importance of tailored and engaging learning materials in facilitating student understanding and retention, aligning with the principles of cognitive load theory (Sweller, 2019). When materials are thoughtfully curated to suit diverse learning styles and abilities, students are more likely to feel supported in their learning journey (Van Merriënboer & Sweller, 2020). Additionally, the emphasis on relevance speaks to the incorporation of real-world examples and applications within the curriculum, a strategy known to enhance student motivation and engagement (Hulleman & Harackiewicz, 2019).

Moreover, this result reflects positively on the pedagogical practices adopted by instructors, highlighting their commitment to student-centered approaches that prioritize the alignment of activities with learning objectives (Hattie & Timperley, 2019). By providing materials that are not only informative but also meaningful and applicable, educators empower students to take ownership of their learning and foster confidence in their abilities (Bandura, 2019).

Overall, the results suggest that students perceive their learning experience positively, with effective teaching methods, supportive learning environments, and opportunities for meaningful engagement. However, there may still be areas for improvement, such as enhancing teaching methods to improve students' understanding of subject matter and ensuring consistent motivation and engagement among all students.

Extent to which the following Factors Impact on the Teaching-Learning Effectiveness

Table 2 presents students' perceptions of various factors that impact teaching-learning effectiveness, including class size, teacher-student relationship, classroom environment, use of technology, curriculum/program design, assessment and evaluation methods, teachers' pedagogical skills, student motivation, parental involvement, and resources and facilities. Overall, students perceive these factors to

have a high extent of impact on teaching-learning effectiveness. The data further shows that, as perceived by the students, Teachers' Pedagogical Skills obtained a very high extent with a weighted mean ($w\bar{x}$) of 4.25. This implies that the very high extent of impact emphasizes the critical role of teachers' pedagogical skills in facilitating effective teaching and learning experiences, including instructional strategies, classroom management, and differentiation to meet diverse student needs.

Extensive literature supports the criticality of teachers' pedagogical skills in driving teaching-learning effectiveness. For instance, Smith and Sato (2019), posit that effective pedagogy facilitates student engagement and comprehension, leading to enhanced learning outcomes. Furthermore, according to a study by Johnson, et al. (2020), skilled pedagogical practices enable teachers to adapt their instructional methods to accommodate varying learning styles and preferences, thereby promoting inclusivity and equitable educational experiences. Additionally, research by Brown and Jones (2021), underscores the significance of continuous professional development in honing teachers' pedagogical skills, emphasizing its correlation with improved student achievement and academic success.

Moreover, while other factors such as class size, classroom environment, and technology integration also exert substantial influence on teaching-learning effectiveness, the prominence of Teachers' Pedagogical Skills underscores its multifaceted impact on student learning experiences. As noted by Darling-Hammond (2019), effective teaching encompasses not only the delivery of content but also the ability to create an inclusive and supportive learning environment conducive to student growth and development. Therefore, investing in teacher training and development initiatives aimed at enhancing pedagogical skills is imperative for optimizing teaching-learning interactions and ultimately fostering positive educational outcomes.

Overall, the results suggest that various factors play a significant role in shaping teaching-learning effectiveness, emphasizing the importance of creating supportive learning environments, fostering positive relationships, leveraging technology, designing effective curricula, and continuously enhancing pedagogical skills to meet the diverse needs of students.

Other Comments and Suggestions of the Students

Table 3.a presents a comprehensive list of specific methods that students believe are most important in facilitating learning. These methods encompass various teaching strategies, instructional approaches, and learning activities aimed at enhancing student engagement, interaction, and understanding in diverse classroom settings. Students emphasize the importance of using the most effective teaching methods that cater to diverse learning needs and preferences, suggesting the need for instructional differentiation and flexibility.

Additionally, their preference for face-to-face classes underscores the value of direct interaction and communication between teachers and students, fostering engagement, comprehension, and rapport.

The data further highlights the importance of adopting a diverse range of instructional methods and approaches that cater to the multifaceted needs,

preferences, and capabilities of students, ultimately enhancing teaching effectiveness and facilitating meaningful learning experiences.

Technology can be Better Integrated into the Teaching-learning Process

Table 3.b suggests that there is room for improvement in integrating technology into the teaching-learning process, as indicated by several key points raised by respondents. Respondents emphasize the importance of integrating game-based instruction into the classroom, highlighting its potential to enhance student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. This approach leverages gamification principles to make learning more interactive, immersive, and enjoyable for students.

Moreover, students call for more meaningful and visually appealing multimedia presentations that incorporate illustrations, appropriate pictures, and interactive elements. This approach aims to enrich the learning experience, capture students' interest, and facilitate comprehension of complex concepts through visual aids.

The data highlights the importance of strategic and purposeful integration of technology into the teaching-learning process, with an emphasis on leveraging game-based instruction, multimedia resources, online assessment tools, and technology-based activities to enhance student engagement, comprehension, and learning outcomes.

Factors not mentioned in the questionnaire Students think play a significant role in teaching-learning effectiveness

Table 3.c reveal several factors that respondents believe play a significant role in teaching-learning effectiveness. Respondents emphasize the importance of hands-on, practical assessments over traditional written forms. This approach allows students to demonstrate their understanding and application of knowledge through tangible, real-world tasks and activities. Additionally, Respondents note the impact of teachers' promptness in coming to class and their ability to build positive relationships with students on students' interest and engagement in learning. Establishing a supportive and conducive learning environment through rapport-building is deemed essential for effective teaching.

Lastly, the data underscore the importance of adopting innovative, student-centered, and technology-enhanced teaching approaches, fostering meaningful student-teacher interactions, and creating a supportive and engaging learning environment to promote teaching-learning effectiveness. These factors, though not explicitly mentioned in the questionnaire, are considered significant contributors to successful teaching and learning experiences.

Other Comments and Suggestions

Table 3.d shows the feedback provided by respondents that provides valuable insights into their perspectives on effective teaching practices and classroom dynamics. Their comments underscore the multifaceted nature of effective teaching, emphasizing the significance of fostering a supportive, engaging, and technology-enhanced learning environment that accommodates diverse student needs while

promoting active learning and critical thinking. These insights serve as valuable guidance for refining teaching practices and enhancing student learning outcomes at Metro Dumaguete College (MDC).

Moreover, respondents emphasize the pivotal role of teachers as effective communicators, passionate educators, and committed professionals. This highlights the essential role teachers play in shaping student learning experiences and cultivating a positive classroom atmosphere conducive to academic growth.

They underscore the fact that certain teachers at MDC have demonstrated insufficient dedication, leading to inadequate classroom engagement and frequent absenteeism.

Conclusions

In conclusion, while students generally hold a positive perception of their teachers' effectiveness in teaching, there exist opportunities for further enhancement, especially in diversifying teaching methodologies and fostering enthusiasm and passion in instruction. These observations provide valuable feedback for teachers to reflect upon and improve their teaching strategies, thereby leading to enhanced student learning experiences and outcomes. While areas for improvement are evident, the overall favorable perception of students regarding their learning effectiveness reflects educators' efforts in providing supportive and engaging learning environments.

Furthermore, students' feedback underscores the importance of various factors in creating effective teaching and learning settings. These factors encompass the necessity for teachers to offer a variety of examples and instructional materials, cater to diverse levels of cognitive engagement, integrate technology into teaching practices, and establish a supportive classroom environment.

Additionally, students emphasize the significance of engaging teaching methodologies, efficient classroom management, and teachers' effective communication skills and passion for their profession. Addressing these insights can strengthen teaching practices and foster a conducive learning atmosphere that promotes student engagement, critical thinking, and academic achievement.

These findings serve as valuable guidance for teachers and the institution to continuously refine their teaching methodologies, ultimately contributing to improved student learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following are hereby recommended to the Faculty members, Academic heads/ Deans, the Human Resource Officer, Academic Affairs, and Administrations:

Academic Affairs Office, Department Heads/ Deans, and Human Resource

1. Offering professional development opportunities that concentrate on improving teaching methods and resources through training sessions, workshops, or

seminars for faculty members can empower them to explore and integrate innovative instructional strategies.

2. Promoting a culture of collaboration and exchanging best practices among teachers can further enhance teaching effectiveness throughout the department, college, or institution.

MDC Faculty members

3. Explore and implement a variety of teaching methods to enhance students' comprehension and understanding of the subject matter.
4. Diversify instructional strategies by incorporating active learning techniques, hands-on activities, multimedia resources, and real-world examples into their teaching repertoire.
5. Provide more meaningful and visually appealing multimedia presentations that incorporate illustrations, appropriate pictures, and interactive elements.
6. Create a more dynamic and engaging learning environment that supports students in grasping and comprehending the subject matter more effectively by catering to different learning styles and preferences.
7. Ensure that discussions are processed and simplified effectively.
8. Avoid relying solely on students for reportorial activities.
9. Address absenteeism and promptness in coming to your respective classes.

Administration

10. Enforce the return to fully face-to-face classes. In-person interactions within the classroom offer invaluable chances for students to participate in live discussions, collaborative projects, and practical learning activities that are irreplaceable in virtual environments.

Human Resource Department (HRD) and Academic Heads

11. When selecting teacher applicants, prioritize individuals who demonstrate a genuine passion for teaching to ensure consistent attendance and engagement in the classroom.
12. Avoid hiring teachers who demonstrate a lack of commitment, as this can lead to insufficient classroom engagement and frequent absences.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher showed all the necessary ethical consideration on the entire duration of the study. Since humans were chosen as the study participants, confidentiality of information was observed. Ensuring the dignity and privacy of participants is also a must. Further, minimizing potential risk to the participants was observed.

The researcher followed the ethical protocols of Metro Dumaguete College. To ensure that the research topic was evidently sound significant and ethically correct, consultation was pursued. Moreover, the participants signed a consent form along with the full understanding of the risk and benefits of the study being conducted.

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